

NDAC/LO/019

1983 April 7

Fourth NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

1. Revised Planning

According to a provisional agreement with the Danish participants, a theoretical and algorithmic study of the PRS Solution will be made in Lund. This task roughly corresponds to WP6200. Some of the programme development (WP6300) could possibly be done here too, in view of the similar computer systems; whether this is expedient should be further discussed. A close interaction with WP5300 in Copenhagen (programme development for the Set Solution) is evidently profitable since several modules for data management and least-squares solution could be almost identical in 5000 and 6000.

Söderhjelm, who is working half-time on the project since the beginning of this year, has started a numerical study of the PRS Solution by means of small-scale simulation. Although his employment after July 1 is still not clear, we assume at least the present level in our planning. A decision by the Swedish Board for Space Activities is expected in May.

The process definition for the PRS Solution (WP6100), due on Febr 28, is in progress and should be completed by the end of April. A delay of six weeks is forecast for the remaining two definitions (WP7100 and 8100).

2. Theory

To enable a stricter formulation of the set observation equations for stars, a new concept 'mean abscissa' was introduced (016). A corresponding problem for minor planets remains to be solved. A simple method for computing pseudo-solutions, compatible with the Cholesky formalism, has been found (018). Suggestions were given for experiments concerning the slit ambiguity solution in Step 3 (83 Jan 31) and the PRS Solution (83 March 18). For the accuracy analysis, modified Step 1/3 error propagation formulae have been proposed (017) and some other topics addressed in various notes and letters.

3. References

- NDAC/LO/016 Definition of mean abscissa (4pp)
 NDAC/LO/017 Error propagation formulae for Step 1 and 3 (22pp)
 NDAC/LO/018 Pseudosolution and pseudocovariance for least-squares problems with known null space (9pp)
 NDAC/LO/019 Fourth NDAC Report from Lund Observatory (1p)
- 1983 Jan 31 Simulation of ambiguity solution by mesh method (3pp)
 1983 Feb 16 Light modulation from the IFOV repositioning (2pp)
 1983 Mar 16 Star Distribution Models (2) (3pp)
 1983 Mar 18 Organization of PRS Experiments (8pp)
 1983 Mar 23 Chromaticity and data reductions (4pp)
 1983 Mar 28 Effect of *a priori* coordinate errors on the abscissa solution (6pp)